

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

Maxliyo Turg'unboyeva

JDPI 2-bosqich talabasi

E - mail: mahliyoturgunboyeva6@gmail.com

Tel: 99 673 40 16

Abstract

Mazkur maqolada ingliz tili o`qitishning zamonaviy metodlari haqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Key words: metodika, chet tili, tarjima metodi, qiyosiy metod, aralash metod, ESES loyihasi, intellektual o`yinlar.

Introduction.

Currently, a lot is being done to develop education. Foreign language teaching is one of the main controls for the state. Because it is not for nothing that knowing the language opens the way to knowing the people, to ensure the creation of a new production FES and the organization of the educational process to obtain national support for the creation of educational projects, the introduction of new technologies and methods and techniques of teaching, the production of knowledge of school students indicates the need for production. The formation of universal educational activity is the main task of education. The student should be encouraged to continue studying life support. And, teachers need to organize their learning activities in a way that they want to distract the student. Active teaching techniques can help the teacher in this.

Methods of activating learning not only help to activate students in the process of physical learning and practical activities, but also help to motivate thinking, reveal and develop creative abilities, help to master the learning material with high efficiency.

The development of modern education has led to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative - in English means "increasing (disseminating) innovation." Socio-medical aspect of the innovation E. E. Rogers, an American researcher.

There is nothing in the world that does not create, and foreign languages are no exception. On the one hand, as social phenomena and systems evolve and improve day by day, the science that studies this phenomenon is also advancing by leaps and bounds. World language - English is developing rapidly. Now there are more and more learners, which means that many teachers and methods are needed to teach this language. If you are a teacher and armed with methodology, it will be easier to learn English.

- Analysis of the literature on the subject (Literature review)

Demand for English is very high now. To do this, a lot of attention is paid to the teaching of this language. As the demand for this language grows, more and more manuals and technologies are being developed to teach English to students. Now I have used such manuals.

If the teacher knows the mental state of the students, he will approach them accordingly. Then they will achieve their goal. They can use appropriate methods and technologies.

The next is “Playing as a Learning Tool for Young Schoolchildren: The Method, Spending”. In this literature there are games for school students to learn the language. It is interesting to learn a language through play. Schoolchildren, in particular, get bored quickly and want the environment to change. Such games help students to overcome fatigue and boredom. Another publication is Jalolov English Methodology of Teaching English, Teacher”. This book, which includes methods of teaching English, is a great guide for teachers. It is easier to learn a language using these methods. I think that Jalolov also did this with this intention and achieved it.

The main part. Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be practiced in the natural environment, is in the family, in the community or in an organized way. Knowledge of linguistic phenomena is taught theoretically. In this age of international relations, language skills are especially important for multilingualism. In ancient times, our ancestors mastered 100 languages and spoke them. Now that we know two languages, we are envious. Why did the former learn? How did they achieve this result. It depends, of course, on professional teachers and coaches. Their knowledge and style are overwhelming. Nowadays, the number of those who consider themselves teachers in parentheses has increased. You can say that we can learn the language ourselves. And for some as a baby gets older, he or she will outgrow this. Having a second language is like comparing the world. If you know your native language grammar, vocabulary, the learning process will accelerate. For example, times, the structure of speech, everything goes by this comparison. Your teacher will explain it to you in his own way, comparing it with your own language. Foreign language and English

This is the desired country language. Western European languages (Spanish, English, German, French) and Eastern languages (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our country. These languages are included in the curricula of educational institutions. Our native language is learned in a natural environment, and a foreign language in an artificial environment. Communication

in a foreign language takes place mainly under the guidance of a teacher in the classroom. This, in turn, requires the use of appropriate training technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of a foreign language teacher in the field of methodology, the student - with the help of the accumulated language - achieves the norm and its accuracy. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methods.

As for the fact that the second language is learned in an artificial environment. You can find and learn the right foreign language for yourself as a teacher and sheik, or you can go abroad and learn it faster. If you want to make learning a second language easier, create a 24-hour artificial environment for yourself. Then it is difficult to read and learning is faster. You will achieve this result if you learn each new word and develop more communication with your friends. Hop we learned how to quickly learn. Now let's talk about effective and fast learning. Methods really help us. Methodologies are our weapons. With methodologies we achieve what we think. What we learn with them is effective and accelerates. We spoke more foreign languages, but I did not mention English because it is one of these languages. But the methods we want to learn will also help us learn the language, of course. Now let's briefly consider one of the techniques. (1)

Intensive method

Firstly began to form at the beginning of the XX century on the basis of the "correct" method. Prof.E.I. Gez said that "the right method provides a favorable opportunity and basis for intensive teaching of a foreign language."

Some of the printsiplial aspects of the correct method are taken as the basis of some of the current modern intensive techniques, such as the need for concoction, the interest in oral speech, especially the choice of speech situations for dialogic speech, the increase in the activity of students in the lesson. This is natural of course, because each new method retains its good sides of the method that has passed before it.

Educational science on the concept of "method" as a general theory of teaching, this term is widely used in science. Deductive interpret the term "method" in the sense of the method of work of the teacher and the student on the way to knowledge, creation of opportunities. For educational subjects that teach the basics of science, universal methods of education are developed. Taking into account the peculiarities of the subject of study, methods of teaching a foreign language are created in the methodology. In the methodology of teaching a foreign language, the term "method" means:

Firstly, the methodology is a whole line in history (the method of translation, the correct method, the comparative method, the mixed method);
Secondly, the system of training, which is part of the above line;
Third, the way in which teachers and students interact. (acquaintance, exercise, methods of application).

The first in the history of Foreign Language Teaching and the second method is referred to by the term 'historical' methods, the third is referred to by the term 'process expression' methods. All the methods in the centuries-old history of teaching a foreign language are grouped into the above four categories. Now we will briefly get acquainted with these techniques.

Translation method

In this method, which itself can be seen by name, a foreign language is the translation of materials into our native language. Some teachers have so far been using non-native methods of translation techniques. For example, the idea of oral translation of the text is a methodological method. It is not forbidden to translate some sentences or two parts of the text. This is to teach the use of the dictionary, which is timed from the point of view of the process.

Among the "translation techniques "the most common are" Grammatics – translation method "and" text – translation method". From the use of both methods of translation only

intended educational purpose. The foreign language is studied in a prescription way. Foreign language teaching methods have been developed based on the data of linguistics and research of their time. This method is one of the most relevant and convenient of the second language teaching. Therefore, it is considered one of our methods of use since history. The main ones of modern innovative pedagogical technologies of teaching English language are the methods. Through the method of translation, you will have an increase in vocabulary, we will learn how to apply words in a compound case,

Correct method

The main reason for the origin of the name of the method is that during the study of the correct method, the mother tongue is bypassed, and the foreign language is arranged between the question and the subject to establish a direct association, that is, a thought connection. the same method was used in teaching English grammar, they wanted to create a direct connection between systematic meaning and the form. Adapting to the second language through this method is quite difficult , but if we do it right, this tilni learning involves a faster deadline. Two of

the modern manifestations of the correct method – audioligual and audiovisual techniques are very common.

Mixed method

This methodology has absorbed the scientific and practical aspects of large methodological directions. Mixed techniques came into existence in the late XIX beginning of the XX century on the basis of a mixture of translated and correct techniques.

Comparative method

Its full name is called "conscious comparative method". One of its first manifestations is a rule – based exercise. In modern appearances, the rule of practical RUC in the process of exercise performance is summarized.

Below we will now be accompanied by more modern techniques. I advise you to familiarize yourself with some of them, I want to note that almost all the techniques are moving and can be used not only in foreign language lessons, but also in other educational disciplines.

1. Organizational stage.

"Carousel" ("Merry Go Round") this technique allows you to use imaginary thinking, memory. The first student receives a card from the teacher and in this word names the associations. The card is transferred along the chain until it returns to the teacher. Each student has the opportunity to express his thoughts at a rapid pace.

Interrogative ("Question Time") is used at different stages of the session. It will be easier for the student to respond to the classmate than to the teacher, and the fear of stiffness and error will disappear. The technique is effective in working with "weak" students so that it can strengthen the material studied and identify gaps in each student. "Surprise" is a method aimed at attracting interest in the activities of the mind and the subject of the lesson. Dependence analysis, separation and formation ability. The teacher finds a point of view that even well-known facts remain a mystery. Puzzle time there are many differences in this methodology, which are successfully used at different stages of the lesson. For example: to find words between a set of letters on a particular topic; ADD WORD words are given, but the letters are left; to solve the CROSSWORD by answering the questions; find the word from the riddles, collect the picture-read the word behind. tongue-twisting turning tools this method is used when practicing correct pronunciation. I always wanted children to learn not only to pronounce this or that sound correctly, but also to make it interesting. You can use picture cards for a specific sound and create the same rhyme. Initially, the teacher will say

the rhyme very slowly, in order to get acquainted with the pronunciation of the vowel. Then the students repeat in small semantic groups after the teacher, and if they hear the given sound in rhyme, they play the chap. Students understand the meaning of words they do not. Then the teacher again loudly pronounces the rhyme, and the children repeat it. And so 3-4 times. Example: Who Laughs Last, do not laugh at best. - the one who laughs last time laughs.

Motivation for educational activities

Problematic situation (question) motivation, interest in the topic, communication, educational background and development of educational and organizational skills will help. The teacher creates a problematic situation, directs the students to solve it, organizes the search for a solution. Thus, the child becomes a learning position, and as a result, new knowledge is formed in it, which he will master new methods of action.

Music part video the teacher prepares a musical fragment, audio recording or video in advance. After listening to a part of the recording or watching a movie, the teacher leads the students to formulate the specific goals, objectives or subject of the lesson through discussion.

Communication is a specific form of communication. This is the interaction between people in training conditions, which is carried out in the form of speech. There is an exchange of information between partners and the relationship between them is regulated. The peculiarity of educational communication is determined by the goals of its participants, the conditions of their interaction. Any such dialogue can be directed to the main topic of the accessible lesson. For example, the topic "your day" can begin with the questions of the teacher in front of the door of the classroom: Good Morning! How do you feel today? When did you get up this morning? Did you have breakfast this morning? Have you done your homework today? What do you plan to do after classes? "Guess the subject" students will be presented with parts of several puzzles. It is necessary to find missing fragments from classmates, form groups and collect puzzles. Then students are asked to guess the subject of the lesson on the basis of the picture taken.

3. Actualization of knowledge.

" Intellectual warm-up ("Magic Ball "or" Snow Ball") at this stage, students "remember" the last material. To develop the ability to speak, the principle of "Intellectual warm-up "can be used during the lesson. As a rule, the lexical bases of such exercises are located in the whiteboard, especially at the initial stage. The growth of the " Snow Ball " can continue in two directions: with an increase in

vocabulary or with an increase in the complexity of vocabulary. (Example: I love reading books\ u003e love reading electronic books. I like to read e-books, because they are easy to use.) Working with Signal cards presentation of this past material in the form of Cards. This method will help to structure the material, restore the attention of students.

Associative line for a specific connotation of the subject or lesson, you need to write in the column words-associations. The way out will be as follows: if the series is relatively correct and adequate, give an assignment to formulate a definition with the help of written words; then listen, compare with the dictionary version, you can add new words to the associative line. Graphic dictator is a great way to enrich your vocabulary and creative thinking skills. Children draw things on the instruction of the teacher, and then sign the words on the drawing.

4. Discover new knowledge.

Catch the mistake universal technique that stimulates the attention of students. Formulate the ability to analysis information, apply knowledge in a non-standard situation. The teacher gives the students information with unknown errors. Students search for errors in a group or separately, argue, give advice. To continue the discussion, students are put on time slots.

"Info-carousel"

Universal technique aimed at arousing interest in the subject of the lesson. Information materials related to the subject of the lesson are arranged in different tables. The class is divided into small groups, depending on the number of tables. Each group gets acquainted with the information on their table and performs the given tasks. After the specified time is over, each group completes work on its desk and moves on to another. Each of the groups works until you visit each data table. On the tables, in addition to the information, there are blank sheets on which small groups write their thoughts. Restorative students will understand the new information they have received with the previous one, use the knowledge they have received at the understanding stage. They choose the most important information to understand the essence of the subject under study. Express new ideas and information in their own words, maintain cause-effect relationships independently. Students must restore part of the text that was intentionally "broken" by the teacher.

"Interesting chain"

"Interesting chain" is a universal technique aimed at updating the knowledge of students of lexical units included in the work. This methodology forms the accumulation of memory and vocabulary on a variety of topics. Example: 1-the

student pronounces the word on the given topic (subject: "adjectives", the word "kind"); 2-the student repeats the first and adds his own word ("kind" - "beautiful"); the third student names the word of the first student, then the second and himself ("kind" - "beautiful" - "smart" ...) and adds others, if the students continue the chain.

"Agree or agree"

This method helps to realize the knowledge of students and to faultless activities. This method allows children to quickly add to mental activity, and it makes sense to switch to the study of the subject of the lesson. Formulate the ability to assess circumstances or circumstances; analyze data; reflect your opinion. The teacher says a number of words on the given topic. It is recommended that children express their relationship during their statements: agree - repeat"+", do not agree - correctly "-". Example: subject - Great Britain. Teacher: 1. London is the capital of the United States. Pupil: No, I do not agree. London is the capital of GB. Teacher: 2. The national language of GB is English. Pupil: Yes, I agree. The national language of GB is English. ...and so on.

5. Joining the knowledge system

Identify errors universal method for activating student attention. Formulate the ability to analysis information; apply knowledge in a non-standard situation; critically evaluate the data obtained.

The teacher gives the students information with unknown errors. Students search for errors in a group or separately, argue, give advice. When it comes to a particular idea, the group chooses the speaker. The speaker submits the results to the teacher or announces the assignment and the result of its solution to the whole class. Set time in advance, so as not to allow the discussion to stretch.

Conclusion.

It is worth noting that, thanks to independence, teachers will be able to use different modern techniques in the course of the lesson. The second language study is a multifaceted teaching, in which a person experiences complex psychological changes in the process. In particular, a comparison of a foreign language with its native language occurs. It benefits from the various methods and technologies of teaching in the process. It is necessary to teach a foreign language and be aware of its methods. There are a lot of such methods. Just need to master it and train. For each teacher, this is a very important process. If we work on our methodology, it is clear that our lessons will pass meaningful and interesting. For this, however, there are a lot of methods and are being tested in the translation. Only it is necessary to learn and apply it all the same. Then the teaching will also

become easy to learn. The work of the teacher and the student will be reduced and effective. Above, we thought about such methods with you. You think, learning English is easy, no, Of course, why you do not know the personalised ways. You know, our teachers method about what a new one learns more agile than us. In it I am not memory, the ability to learn is slowed down. But their ASOI weapons are not those – but-methods, pedagogical methods. Teachers are therefore considered very easy to improve their knowledge. Another example of this: the teacher has mastered the lexicon, but with the C1 certificate, the knowledge of his students does not improve. From what it is, you know. Of course in the methodology. Therefore, we did not call the teachers the main weapon – methodology. Qualification classes are also ready to teach. New games, cheerful cattons or vedios, puzzling puzzles are all methods of teaching this lesson.

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